

MELT PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES OF POLYAMIDE 6/GRAPHENE NANOPLETELET COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the processing and characterization of Polyamide 6 (PA6) / graphite nanoplatelets (GNPs) composites is reported. PA6/GNPs composites were prepared by melt-mixing using an industrial, co-rotating, intermeshing, twin-screw extruder. A bespoke screw configuration was used that was designed in-house to enhance nanoparticle dispersion into a polymer matrix. The effects of GNPs type (xGnP® M-5 and xGnP® C-500), GNPs content, and extruder screw speed on the bulk properties of the PA6/GNPs nanocomposites were investigated. Results show a considerable improvement in the thermal and mechanical properties of PA6/GNPs composites, as compared with the unfilled PA6 polymer. An increase in crystallinity (%X_c) with increasing GNPs content, and a change in shape of the crystallization exotherms (broadening) and melting endotherms, both suggest a change in the crystal type and perfection. An increase in tensile modulus of as much as 376% and 412% was observed for PA6/M-5 xGnP® and PA6/C-500 xGnP® composites, respectively, at filler contents of 20wt%. The enhancement of Young's modulus and yield stress can be attributed to the reinforcing effect of GNPs and their uniform dispersion in the PA6 matrix. The rheological response of the composite resembles that of a 'pseudo-solid', rather than a molten liquid, and analysis of the rheological data indicates that a percolation threshold was reached at GNPs contents of between 10–15wt%. The electrical conductivity of the composite also increased with increasing GNPs content, with an addition of 15wt% GNPs resulting in a 6 order-of-magnitude increase in conductivity. The electrical percolation thresholds of all composites were between 10–15wt%.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years graphene, due to its outstanding properties, has become the topic of much research activity [1-4]. Single layer graphene with a Young's modulus of 1TPa and an ultimate strength of 130 GPa is the strongest material ever measured [4]. As a conductor of electricity it performs as well as copper. As a conductor of heat it outperforms all other known materials. It is almost completely transparent, yet so dense that not even helium, the smallest gas atom, can pass through it [5]. Graphene which is a 2D monolayer of carbon atoms has a significant number of potential advantages over its 1D cousin, carbon nanotubes. Because it is 2D, property enhancement will also be 2D [6]. An even greater advantage is likely to emerge in the future as the use of CNTs in plastic components is provoking fears about toxicity potential [7] that, due to its 2D nature, graphene is unlikely to exhibit. In comparison with nanoclays, graphene has the huge advantage of being conductive coupled with much superior mechanical properties (178 GPa modulus compared with 1TPa for Graphene). There is also the potential of much larger particle dimensions than available with naturally occurring nanoclays. The potential applications for this material are enormous particularly if it can be successfully incorporated into polymers by conventional polymer processing routes. Applications include low cost, light weight, EMI shielded computer housings and cables, anti-static packaging, lightweight, high strength automotive and aerospace components, high barrier packaging and smart clothing/personal sensor systems. The multifunctionality of graphene combined with its relatively low cost methods of production makes this a unique material.

Many researchers globally are currently engaged in finding the best way of producing high quality graphene on a large scale. Recent research by Drzal et al. has shown that it is feasible to exfoliate natural graphite into nanoplatelets having thicknesses <10nm and diameters of tens of microns in size [8, 9]. This material, which is known as exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets (xGnP[®]), has a platelet morphology with a surface area of more than 100m²/g a, thickness of ≤10nm and a diameter that can be controlled by adjusting the milling conditions. Since xGnP is based on very affordable and still abundant natural graphite, the cost is expected to be substantially lower than other carbon materials [10].

The objective of the research was to determine if it is possible to enhance both the mechanical and electrical properties of thermoplastic polymers by incorporating GNPs via melt mixing. Polyamide 6 (PA6) was chosen as the matrix material due to its engineering property profile and significant commercial interest. The morphology, rheological, thermal, structural, mechanical and electrical behaviour of the composites was investigated to assess the influence of GNP content and extruder screw speed on the properties of the resulting nanocomposites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

BASF Ultramid B40L (Relative Viscosity 3.89 - 4.17) Polyamide 6 (PA6) was supplied in pellet form by Ultrapolymers. The PA6 pellets were cryogenically ground to a fine powder (µm) using a Wedco SE-12 UR pilot plant grinding mill at 7000 rpm and a gap size set to 400 µm using liquid nitrogen for temperature regulation. xGnP[®] Graphene Nanoplatelets were supplied by XG Sciences. Technical specifications of these GNPs are detailed in Table 1:

GRADE	Product	# layers	Thickness (nm)	Diameter (µm)	Surf. Area (m ² /g)
M	M-5	18-24	6-8	5	120-150
C	C-500	2-15	1-5	1-2	500

Table 1: xGnP[®] Graphene Nanoplatelet technical specifications.

2.2 Composite Preparation

The ground PA6 powder was dried at 80 °C for 12 hours prior to mixing. Pre-dried PA6 powder and GNPs, were pre-mixed at 1 wt%, 3wt%, 5 wt%, 7.5 wt% and 10 wt% graphene using a Thermo Scientific Prism Pilot 3 High Speed Mixer at 2000rpm for 2 mins. The melt-mixing process was performed using a co-rotating intermeshing twin-screw extruder (Collin GmbH), having a screw diameter of 25 mm and a barrel length of 750 mm (L/D=30). On exiting the capillary die the extrudate was drawn through a cooled water bath at a constant haul off rate and pressure. The extrudate was dried by passing through an air ring and then pelletized using a Collin Pelletiser. A bespoke screw configuration designed to enhance nanoparticle dispersion into polymeric matrices was used [11]. The process conditions used for each experiment and are shown in Table 2. The extruded pellets were dried in the oven at 80°C for 4 hours before compression moulding. Samples were compression moulded in a platen press at 250°C for 3 mins at 150 bars.

Extruder Zones	Z1	Z2	Z3	Z4	Z5	Z6	Die
Temperature (°C)	185	245	240	240	240	235	240
Screw Rotation direction	Co-rotating						
Screw Speed (rpm)	Low Speed=50rpm			High Speed=200rpm			
GNPs Loading (wt%)	1%	3%	5%	7.5%	10%	15%	20%

Table 2- Process conditions set up for PA6/GNP extrusion in the twin screw extruder.

2.3 Characterization

The morphology and the degree of dispersion of GNPs in the PET matrix were investigated using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Samples for SEM analysis were plasma etched for 60s at an etching power of 100w using a reactive ion etching system (STS Cluster C005) and then gold sputtered prior to imaging. These samples were examined using a JEOL 6500F Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) with an operating voltage of 5 kV.

GNPs dispersion was investigated further using oscillatory melt rheology. Dynamic rheological measurements were performed using an AR-G2 Oscillatory Rheometer and Rheology Advantage Instrument Control AR Software. The measurements were carried out in oscillatory shear mode using parallel plate geometry (Standard ETC Steel plate, 25 mm diameter, 1 mm gap) at 240 °C. Frequency sweeps from 100 rad/s to 0.1 rad/s were carried out at low strains (1%) which were shown to be within the linear viscoelastic limit of all the materials of interest.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed on samples of unfilled PA6 and PA6/GNP composites using a Perkin–Elmer DSC model 6 under an inert nitrogen atmosphere using a heating and cooling rate of 10 K/min. between 30°C and 275°C. In all cases the samples were held at 275 °C for 3 min., then cooled to 30°C at 10K/min. and reheated again to 275°C at 10 K/min. to ensure complete melting of the crystalline fraction of PA6 and to remove thermal history. The apparent crystalline content of the composites was determined using a value of 191J/g for the heat of fusion for a theoretically 100% crystalline PA6.

Tensile tests were carried out (BS EN ISO 527-1: 1996) using an Instron 5564 Universal Tester with a clip-on extensometer at room temperature. A kN load cell was used. Samples were prepared by compression moulding, from which dumbbell-shaped samples (type 1BA) were cut using a stamping press. For modulus measurement, nominal strain was determined using an extensometer attached on the narrow portion of the dumb-bell samples at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min and a gauge length of 25 mm. Whereas for the strength and elongation, the nominal strain was derived from the grip

displacement at a crosshead speed of 50 mm/min., modulus was determined from the slope of the regression of the stress-strain data between 0.05 - 0.25 % strain.

Volume resistivity measurements were performed on compression moulded samples of all nanocomposites of thickness 1 mm. For high resistivity samples, a Keithley electrometer (Model 6517A) equipped with an 8009 test fixture with circular samples of diameter 60 mm was used. The sample of interest was placed between two circular electrodes and the volume resistivity measured by applying a DC voltage potential across opposite sides of the sample and measuring the resultant current through the sample. This test conforms to ASTM D-257. For more conductive samples ($< 10^7 \Omega \text{ cm}$) strips with dimensions of $50 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ were cut from the sheets and measured using a Keithley electrometer (Model DMM 2000) using a two-point test fixture (i.e. contact wires with a distance of 50 mm between the measuring electrodes).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SEM micrographs of representative samples of PA6/10%C-500 at 50rpm and PA6/20%C-500 at 200rpm are shown in Fig.1. The GNPs appear to be well dispersed in the polymer matrix, with agglomeration increasing with increasing GNPs content.

Fig. 1: FESEM photomicrograph of PA6/GNPs after plasma etching process.

The rheological properties of unfilled PA6 and PA6/M-5 composites were measured in a series of dynamic frequency sweep tests from 100 rad.s^{-1} to 0.1 rad.s^{-1} at a constant temperature of 240°C within the viscoelastic limit of all materials of interest (1% strain). The rheological results, including storage modulus (G') and complex viscosity (η^*), of unfilled PP and PA6/GNPs composites are shown in Figure 2 in the form of log-log plots.

Unfilled PA6 exhibits non-Newtonian behaviour, where viscous behaviour dominates at low frequencies ($G' \sim \omega^2$) and polymer chain entanglements at higher frequencies, while the composites with 5 wt%, 10 wt%, 15 wt% and 20 wt% GNPs exhibit a clear transition to shear-thinning behaviour. G' increased on the addition of GNPs to PA6, especially at low frequencies, where the instrument is most sensitive to changes in melt-flow behaviour. As expected, the addition of high aspect ratio and high modulus GNPs increases G' and η^* of the PA6 matrix by an order of magnitude. As expected, the addition of GNPs, increased η^* and G' of PA6 (Figure 2a and Figure 2b). A rheological percolation threshold was obtained between 10-15 wt% GNPs, as indicated by an increase in η^* and G' at low frequencies where the rheological response of the composite is more like a 'pseudo-solid' than a molten liquid.

Fig.2: Variation in (a) storage modulus (G') as a function of frequency (ω); (b) complex viscosity (η^*) as a function of ω for unfilled PA6 and PA6/M5 composites.

A rheological percolation is achieved when an interconnected network of GNPs and GNP agglomerates restricts polymer chain motion [12]. Therefore, oscillatory rheology analysis is a sensitive method for detecting the formation of percolated MWCNT networks, manifest by a distinct change in viscoelastic behavior due to restricted polymer chain mobility caused by the presence of CNTs [11, 13-15]. As expected, the addition of GNPs, increased η^* and G' of PA6 (Figure 2a and Figure 2b). A rheological percolation threshold was obtained between 10-15 wt% GNPs, as indicated by an increase in η^* and G' at low frequencies where the rheological response of the composite is more like a 'pseudo-solid' than a molten liquid. It is possible to observe also from the Cole-Cole plots that the slopes of the curves decrease when increasing GNP content. This is also an indication of the transition from 'liquid-like' to 'solid-like' behaviour due to the well-dispersed MWCNTs restricting polymer chain mobility. At low frequencies, the curves for the 5 wt%, 10 wt%, 15 wt% and 20 wt% GNP composites form a plateau, implying percolation was achieved, as an increase in $\tan \delta^{-1}$ is a measure of the increase in 'solidity' of the composite. Similar trends were found for PP/MWCNT composites produced by melt-mixing with a rheological percolation ~ 0.5 wt% MWCNTs being reported [16].

To our knowledge, there are very few publications of polymer/GNPs nanocomposite oscillatory rheology studies and none on PA6/xGnP. In oscillatory rheological studies of PP/GNPs by Kalaitzidou et al., the results show a rheological percolation threshold of $\sim 10\%$ vol GNPs for both xGnP-1 and xGnP-15. They also found a larger increase in G' for xGnP-1 resulting in stiffer composites, probably as a result of the larger number of xGnP-1 particles compared to the number of particles contained in the same volume fraction of xGnP-15 [10].

Thermal analysis using DSC was performed to study the effect of GNPs addition on the melting and crystallisation behaviour of PA6. The crystallization temperature (T_c), melting temperature (T_m), enthalpies of fusion (ΔH) and crystalline content (X_c) were determined and are shown in Table 3. By way of example, Fig. 3 shows the DSC thermograms for the first cooling run and the second heating run (to delete thermal history) for neat PA6 and the PA6/C-500 GNPs composites.

50rpm	First heat				Cooling			Second heat			
	T _m (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	X _c (%)	Impr (%)	T _c (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	T _m (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	X _c (%)	Impr (%)	
PA6 Unfilled	221.5	73.2	38.3		180.3	68.5	221.9	66.5	34.8		
PA6/ 1wt% M-5	221.8	98.9	51.8	35.1	182.4	85.6	222.2	90.3	47.3	35.8	
PA6/ 3wt% M-5	221.9	117.4	61.5	60.4	183.5	86.0	222.4	95.6	50.1	43.7	
PA6/ 5wt% M-5	222.2	125.7	65.8	71.7	184.5	89.8	222.1	112.4	58.8	69.0	
PA6/ 7.5wt% M-5	222.5	134.6	70.5	83.9	185.6	105.6	222.2	124.9	65.4	87.8	
PA6/ 10wt% M-5	222.4	142.9	74.8	95.2	185.8	112.0	222.6	137.1	71.8	106.2	
PA6/ 15wt% M-5	223.5	151.9	79.5	107.5	186.1	115.9	223.1	142.3	74.5	114.0	
PA6/ 20wt% M-5	223.9	155.0	81.2	111.7	186.7	116.7	223.3	145.9	76.4	119.4	
50rpm	First heat				Cooling			Second heat			
	T _m (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	X _c (%)	Impr (%)	T _c (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	T _m (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	X _c (%)	Impr (%)	
PA6 Unfilled	221.5	73.2	38.3		180.3		221.9	66.5	34.8		
PA6/ 1wt% C-500	221.9	115.3	60.3	57.5	183.2	1.61	221.8	112.6	59.0	69.3	
PA6/ 3wt% C-500	221.6	127.7	66.8	74.4	183.9	2.00	222.1	126.9	66.4	90.8	
PA6/ 5wt% C-500	222.1	135.2	70.8	84.7	184.1	2.11	222.4	135.8	71.1	104.2	
PA6/ 7.5wt% C-500	221.9	147.0	77.0	100.8	185.3	2.77	222.5	138.0	72.3	107.5	
PA6/ 10wt% C-500	222.3	149.7	78.4	104.5	185.2	2.72	222.3	140.7	73.7	111.6	
PA6/ 15wt% C-500	222.5	152	79.6	107.6	185.4	2.83	223.2	143.4	75.1	115.6	
PA6/ 20wt% C-500	223.9	154.1	80.7	110.5	186.1	3.22	223.3	145.6	76.2	118.9	
200rpm	First heat				Cooling			Second heat			
	T _m (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	X _c (%)	Impr (%)	T _c (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	T _m (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	X _c (%)	Impr (%)	
PA6 Unfilled	222.6	71.5	37.4		179.6	70.7	222.3	68.0	35.6		
PA6/ 1wt% M-5	222.2	111.7	58.5	56.2	183.8	91.0	222.6	97.0	50.8	42.6	
PA6/ 3wt% M-5	222.3	125.1	65.5	75.0	184.1	89.2	222.6	100.7	52.7	48.1	
PA6/ 5wt% M-5	222.6	134.5	70.4	88.1	184.5	90.4	222.4	115.3	60.3	69.5	
PA6/ 7.5wt% M-5	222.6	140.6	73.6	96.6	185.1	118.4	222.2	136.0	71.2	100.0	
PA6/ 10wt% M-5	222.6	149.4	78.2	108.9	185.2	118.3	222.1	142	74.4	108.8	
PA6/ 15wt% M-5	224.0	156.4	81.9	118.7	186.4	117.4	223.3	148.7	77.9	118.7	
PA6/ 20wt% M-5	224.7	158.9	83.2	122.2	187.7	118.5	223.9	149.4	78.2	119.7	
200rpm	First heat				Cooling			Second heat			
	T _m (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	X _c (%)	Impr (%)	T _c (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	T _m (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	X _c (%)	Impr (%)	
PA6 Unfilled	222.6	71.5	37.4		179.6	70.7	222.3	68.0	35.6		
PA6/ 1wt% C-500	222.5	128.1	67.1	79.2	184.4	112.7	222.7	126.3	66.1	85.7	
PA6/ 3wt% C-500	221.9	136.2	71.3	90.5	184.8	115.6	222.4	132.1	69.2	94.3	
PA6/ 5wt% C-500	221.7	142.3	74.5	99.0	184.8	115.4	222.1	140.4	73.5	106.5	
PA6/ 7.5wt% C-500	221.9	150.4	78.7	110.3	185.7	112.2	222.6	142.9	74.8	110.1	
PA6/ 10wt% C-500	222.1	151.5	79.3	111.9	186.2	113.9	222.1	145.7	76.3	114.3	
PA6/ 15wt% C-500	222.7	154.8	81.0	116.5	186.9	110.3	222.9	146.3	76.6	115.1	
PA6/ 20wt% C-500	224.5	155.1	81.2	116.9	186.6	108.0	223.8	148.3	77.6	118.1	

Table 3: Effect of M-5 and C-500 GNPs addition on the thermal properties of unfilled PA6 and PA6/GNPs composites at two different screw speeds 50 and 200rpm.

Thermal analysis using DSC was performed to study the effect of GNP addition on the melting and crystallisation behaviour of PA6. Figure 4 show the DSC thermograms for the first cooling run and the second heating run (to delete thermal history) for neat PA6 and the PA6/GNPs composites. The crystallization temperature (T_c), melting temperature (T_m), enthalpies of fusion (ΔH) and crystalline content (X_c) are shown in Table 3. The addition of GNPs had little effect on the glass transition temperature (T_g) (not shown in the table) and melting temperature (T_m) of PA6. However, the addition of GNPs significantly increases the crystallinity of the PA6 and T_c is also significantly increased. This is indicative of a strong nucleation effect by the GNPs. It is also clear from the melting endotherms in Fig. 3 that there are two melting peaks in the unfilled PA6 and only one in the materials containing GNPs. This second peak may be due to the presence of some γ form crystallites which have a melting point approximately 10°C below the main melting point of the α form crystals or it may be due to the early melting of less perfect α crystallites. The second melting peak is not evident in the material containing GNPs, indicating that the γ crystallites are no longer present. From Figure 3 it can also be observed that the cooling curves for the composites containing C-500 xGNPs have a double peak but this is absent in the cooling curves for the M-5 xGNPs and for the unfilled PA6. It is not clear the cause of this behavior and more studies are required. The effect of increasing the screw speed is to increase slightly the % X_c which may be due to the fact that the dispersion improves when the screw speed increases thus creating more nucleation sites.

It is clear that both X_c and T_c increase when the % of addition of xGNP increases for both types of xGNP and for both extrusion speeds. It is also possible to observe that the rate of initial increase in crystallinity is greater for PA6/C-500 composites than for the PA6/M-5 composites. This may be due to the different size and aspect ratio of the xGNPs; C-500 having smaller and thinner particles which may act as a better nucleating agent thus increasing crystallization rate in the PA6 matrix.

Fig.3: DSC showing; (a) crystallization exotherms and (b) melting endotherms (2nd heating cycle for unfilled PA6 and PA6/C-500 composites.

The tensile properties of neat PA6 and the PA6/GNPs composites were measured and Young's modulus was determined, as shown in Table 4.

50rpm		Modulus (MPa)	Impr* (%)	50rpm		Modulus (MPa)	Impr* (%)
PA 6 unfilled	Mean	1136.5		PA 6 unfilled	Mean	1136.5	
	SD	97			SD	97	
PA6/1%M-5	Mean	1345.3	18.4	PA6/1%C-500	Mean	1457.9	28.3
	SD	47			SD	45	
PA6/3%M-5	Mean	1390.9	22.4	PA6/3%C-500	Mean	1683.3	48.1
	SD	58			SD	85	
PA6/5%M-5	Mean	1450.7	27.6	PA6/5%C-500	Mean	1892.7	66.5
	SD	36			SD	51	
PA6/7.5%M-5	Mean	1672.8	47.2	PA6/7.5%C-500	Mean	2170.9	91.0
	SD	57			SD	108	
PA6/10%M-5	Mean	3003.9	164.3	PA6/10%C-500	Mean	2573.7	126.5
	SD	101			SD	76	
PA6/15%M-5	Mean	4910.7	332.1	PA6/15%C-500	Mean	3700.9	225.6
	SD	89			SD	78	
PA6/20%M-5	Mean	5410.7	376.1	PA6/20%C-500	Mean	5793.5	409.8
	SD	158			SD	102	
200rpm		Modulus (MPa)	Impr* (%)	200rpm		Modulus (MPa)	Impr* (%)
PA 6 unfilled	Mean	1285.7		PA 6 unfilled	Mean	1285.7	
	SD	69			SD	69	
PA6/1%M-5	Mean	1468.0	14.2	PA6/1%C-500	Mean	1639.9	27.6
	SD	83			SD	80	
PA6/3%M-5	Mean	1494.0	16.2	PA6/3%C-500	Mean	1877.6	46.0
	SD	59			SD	72	
PA6/5%M-5	Mean	1726.0	34.3	PA6/5%C-500	Mean	2174.6	69.1
	SD	67			SD	99	
PA6/7.5%M-5	Mean	1880.0	46.2	PA6/7.5%C-500	Mean	2437.9	89.6
	SD	92			SD	84	
PA6/10%M-5	Mean	3644.8	183.5	PA6/10%C-500	Mean	2956.2	129.9
	SD	104			SD	116	
PA6/15%M-5	Mean	5269.3	309.9	PA6/15%C-500	Mean	4244.4	230.1
	SD	94			SD	75	
PA6/20%M-5	Mean	6142.0	377.7	PA6/20%C-500	Mean	6584.1	412.1
	SD	140			SD	93	

* with respect to PA6 unfilled

Table 4: Effect of addition of M-5 and C-500 GNPs to mechanical properties of PA6 unfilled and PA6/ GNPs composites at two different screw speeds 50 and 200rpm.

For the PA6/ M-5 GNPs composites at 50 rpm, the tensile modulus shows an increase with respect to the PA6 unfilled of 28% at 5% GNPs, 164% at 10% GNPs and 376% GNPs addition with a maximum of 5410MPa at a 20wt% loading of GNPs. For the 200 rpm material the tensile modulus increases slightly more with a maximum of 6142MPa (378% increase respect PA6 unfilled) at 20 wt% loading.

For the PA6/ C-500 GNPs composites at 50 rpm, the tensile modulus shows an increase with respect to the PA6 unfilled of 66% at 5% GNPs, 126% at 10% GNPs and 410% GNPs addition with a maximum of 5793MPa at a 20wt% loading of GNPs. For the 200 rpm material the tensile modulus increases slightly more with a maximum of 6584MPa (412% increase respect PA6 unfilled) at 20 wt% loading.

For both types of xGNPs (M-5 and C-500) and for both extrusion speeds (50 and 200 rpm), Young's modulus and crystallinity increase with increases in the GNPs loading. There is a large initial increase in crystallinity when GNPs are added (from 0% to 1wt% addition). This is accompanied by a small increase in the modulus, some of which is likely attributable to the increasing crystallinity and the absence of γ form crystallites, which have a lower Young's modulus than the α form. Crystallinity levels increase relatively slowly after 1wt% addition of GNPs, with little accompanying increase in modulus for the M-5 xGNPs, and small increases for C-500 xGNPs. After 10wt% GNPs, crystallinity is relatively unchanged, but the modulus continues to increase significantly for M-5 and C-500 xGNPs, indicating that modulus increase here is not associated with crystallinity but with increasing GNPs content.

Fig. 4 shows the change in electrical properties of the composites as the loading of particles is increased. The conductivity in the M-5 composites increases very slowly with increasing GNPs content up to 8wt% and then increases at a faster rate, similar to the Young's modulus enhancement. For the C-500 particles there is again a gradual increase in conductivity with increasing particle loading however the maximum conductivity achieved is lower than that for the M-5 particles at the higher extrusion speed. Increasing extrusion speed has the effect of increasing the conductivity of the composites which is likely to be due to a better dispersion of the nanoparticles in the matrix.

Fig.4: Effect of addition of M-5 and C-500 GNPs to electrical resistivity properties of PA6 unfilled and PA6/ GNPs composites at two different screw speeds 50 and 200rpm.

Unfortunately, in the SEM images it is not possible to detect a significant difference between the structure of the PA6/10%GNPs and the PA6/20%GNPs structure that would indicate the absence/presence of conductive networks. Such networks are thought to contain pathways of connecting agglomerates of varying sizes and individual platelets and their formation is governed by the degree of GNPs dispersion and distribution in the PA6 matrix [17].

4 CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions may be drawn regarding the effect of extrusion screw speed and particle loading level on the microscopic, rheological, thermal, mechanical and electrical properties of PA6/GNPs composites:

From the SEM images, the nanoplatelets appear well dispersed in the polymer matrix and agglomerations tend to increase when increasing the GNPs content.

A rheological percolation threshold was obtained between 10-15 wt% GNPs, as indicated by an increase in η^* and G' at low frequencies, the rheological response of the composite is more like a 'pseudo-solid' than a molten liquid.

From the XRD results, PA6 exhibits two main diffraction peaks attributed to the α -phase, which indicates that the α -form crystals are the dominant crystalline phase. The graphite diffraction peak appears with the addition of GNPs. As % GNPs increases the α peaks shift and change intensity slightly, which indicates a change in the preferential growth of the PA6 crystal planes.

The addition of GNPs to PA6 matrix has the effect of dramatically increasing the crystallinity by 110-120% for 20wt% GNP addition to the PA6 matrix. Increasing screw speed from 50rpm to 200rpm has the effect of slightly increasing from 3-5% of crystallinity.

A maximum increase of between 375-420% in tensile modulus is achieved at a loading of 20wt% GNPs in PA6. Increasing the screw speed increases the tensile modulus by an additional 10-15wt%. The enhancement in Young's modulus can be attributed to the reinforcing effect of GNPs.

The electrical conductivity increased as the weight fraction of GNPs increased, showing an increase of about 6 orders of magnitude on the addition of up to 15 wt% GNPs. The electrical percolation threshold for the composites melt-mixed at 50 and 200 rpm for both M-5 and C-500 GNPs is identified between 10-15 wt% GNPs. Increasing extrusion speed has the effect of increasing the conductivity of the composites which is likely to be due to a better dispersion of the nanoparticles in the matrix.

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